

Parasitic peritonitis : when nematode doesn't need any perforation

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Introduction

Acute abdominal pain in a patient hospitalized for a severe infectious disease poses a diagnostic challenge, particularly when there are few specific signs and when the etiology is uncommon. The coexistence of vascular and parasitic causes in peritonitis is rare and may surprise the surgeon, especially in the absence of evident macroscopic digestive perforation. We report an unusual case of peritonitis associated with mesenteric ischemia and the presence of nematodes.

Case Presentation

The patient is a 35-year-old man, a known heavy drinker, initially hospitalized in cardiology for *Staphylococcus aureus* endocarditis due to pacemaker infection, treated with vancomycin. Ten days after admission, he presented with diffuse abdominal pain, vomiting, bowel dysfunction, abdominal guarding and deterioration in his general condition. Abdominal CT scan showed inflammatory small bowel without obvious signs of obstruction. Given the clinical picture suggestive of acute abdomen, exploratory laparotomy was indicated. Exploration revealed signs of mesenteric ischemia, probably caused by endocarditis, an inflammatory segment of ileum and bacterial translocation peritonitis without macroscopic digestive perforation. Peritoneal samples were taken, followed by thorough lavage of the peritoneum. The laboratory revealed the presence of nematodes in peritoneum. The patient was treated with broad-spectrum antibiotic therapy including ertapenem (Invanz), vancomycin and teicoplanin (Targocid), antifungal therapy with fluconazole, antiparasitic therapy with albendazole, and anticoagulation for mesenteric ischemia. One week later, the clinical outcome is considered favorable, according to imaging.

Conclusion

This case illustrates a rare and complex form of peritonitis combining mesenteric ischemia, bacterial infection and parasitosis, without macroscopic digestive perforation. It highlights the importance of surgical exploration and multidisciplinary management in establishing a diagnosis.

Keywords

Nematode ; Laparotomy ; Perforation